
Interoperable as in FAIR

— A librarian's personal point of view —

Patricia Herterich - University of Birmingham - @pherterich

What's interoperability?

"the ability of computer systems or software to exchange and make use of information."

[Oxford dictionary <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/interoperability> via <https://software.ac.uk/blog/2018-10-26-interoperability-and-its-importance-research-software>]

FAIR principles

“The FAIR principles are a set of community-developed guidelines to ensure that data or any digital object are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. The FAIR principles specifically emphasize enhancing the ability of machines to automatically find and use data or any digital object, and support its reuse by individuals. Standards for the description, interoperability, citation etc. are at the core of these principles.”

Source: International Neuroinformatics Coordinating Facility (INCF)

<https://web.archive.org/web/20181230175649/https://www.incf.org/activities/standards-and-best-practices/what-is-fair>

State of Open Data report 2018

1872 responses:

- 60 % of respondents had never heard of FAIR principles
- 15 % consider themselves familiar with them and
 - 41% felt that Interoperable needed better definition, compared to 13% for Findable, 19% for Accessible and 26% for Reusable

H2020 - Data Management Plan templates

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

Horizon 2020 DMP survey report

Unknown, unclear or confusing terminology:

Marjan Grootveld, Ellen Leenarts, Sarah Jones, Emilie Hermans, & Eliane Fankhauser. (2018). OpenAIRE and FAIR Data Expert Group survey about Horizon 2020 template for Data Management Plans (Version 1.0.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1120245>

How is this assessed?

- DANS FAIR data assessment tool prototype
 - Is the dataset multi-file?
 - Is the data file in a proprietary format?
- ARDC FAIR Data self-assessment tool:
 - What (file) format(s) is the data available in?
 - What best describes the types of vocabularies/ontologies/tagging schemas used to define the data elements?
 - How is the metadata linked to other data and metadata (to enhance context and clearly indicate relationships)?

FAIR for software?

Interoperability:

- Use of open, community-standard formats for data
- Greater use of platform/plugin architectures
- Use of common libraries and package managers

Chue Hong, Neil; Katz, Daniel S. (2018): FAIR enough? Can we (already) benefit from applying the FAIR data principles to software?.
figshare. Presentation. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7449239.v2>

Standards! Yay!?

Source: xkcd, <http://xkcd.com/927/>

There are tools...

FAIRsharing.org
standards, databases, policies

Search all of FAIRsharing

Standards

Databases

Policies

Collections

Add/Claim Content

Stats

Log in or Register

A curated, informative and educational resource on data and metadata *standards*, inter-related to *databases* and data *policies*.

**1294
standards...**

HOW CAN WE HELP?

We guide consumers to discover, select and use these resources with confidence, and producers to make their resource more discoverable, more widely adopted and cited.

Researchers in academia, industry and government

Identify and cite the standards, databases or repositories that exist for your discipline when creating a data management plan, releasing data or submitting a manuscript to a journal...

[\[read more\]](#)

Researchers

Developers & Curators

Journal Publishers

Librarians & Trainers

Societies & Alliances

Funders

How do we teach this?

- LIBER recommendation: “Train subject and data librarians on disciplinary metadata, vocabularies and tools to make data FAIR”

(<https://libereurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/12/LIBER-FAIR-Data.pdf>)

- This is barely covered in Library Schools any longer
- How do we train researchers on this?
 - Library Carpentry - Top 10 FAIR Data & Software Things
<https://librarycarpentry.org/Top-10-FAIR/>
 - Library Carpentry - Under design: lesson on “Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) Data and Software”

Opinions? Ideas?

- Find me over coffee
- Record a podcast with me discussing FAIR principles :)
- Tweet me @pherterich